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**2018 Conference on Education and Global Conflict Resolution,
Nwafor Orizu College of Education Nsugbe, Anambra State, Nigeria.
In Collaboration with the School of External Studies,
Makerere University, Republic of Uganda.**

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OBJECTIVES:

International Journal of Topical Issues(IJTI) is a peer-reviewed journal that publishes original empirical and theoretical papers on current educational issues across the globe. The journal is multidisciplinary, therefore it accepts papers from various fields of study relating to education: research, sciences, social sciences, vocational studies, languages and information technology (ICT).

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INTRODUCTION

It is with great pleasure that we present the second volume of our *International Journal of Topical Issues (IJTI)*. This volume deals with Education and Global Conflict Resolution. In this editorial introduction, we do not intend to x-ray the contents of each article but to underline the basic attitude, which the reader should adopt while reading them. Reading other people's articles is a waste of information until such a reading speaks to the personal experience of the reader. The reader should be able to reflect on these articles. Reflection presupposes that every human experience is a reservoir of tremendous knowledge and information.

Our ability and capacity to use our reason to sift and critically examine the information contained in each article is what makes a difference between an ordinary reader and a scholar. Our rational capacity can be developed through critical reading and asking questions in contrast to just reading and accepting the status quo without reflecting on them. When you read this journal, do not take everything the writer says as a gospel truth but take a little time to think of other possibilities other than what a particular author says. Find out whether you agree or disagree with the author.

This volume contains a number of interesting articles such as: Education and global peace resolution; The philosophy of global conflict resolution: education and the educator's competence to implementing it, the case of schools in East Africa Uganda in particular; Beyond extant procedures: The essentiality of ethical education as toolkit and lubricating oil for engineering functional global religious conflict resolution; Value education in Teacher institutions: A recipe for peace in Sub-Saharan Africa; Conflict convergence or co-existence: the strategic logic of education in reframing world order. We invite you to a more critical reading of these articles so that you may discover more alternatives that may be inherent in these essays.

Finally, our sincere gratitude go to reviewers, the editors, the members of the editorial board, the consulting editors and all who made the publication of this volume possible.

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RESOLVING THE GLOBAL CONFLICT IN EDUCATION THROUGH AWARENESS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS AMONG CHEMISTRY STUDENTS

Nnoli, J. N. Ph.D

&

Sambo, D. D.

Abstract

This paper discusses the global conflicts in education and its' resolution through creating awareness of the skills enshrined in chemistry education and the challenges of inculcation of the skills to students which they can venture into after graduation for self employment. Five research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. A descriptive survey design was used. Three hundred (300) SS3 chemistry students drawn from 45 secondary schools out of 258 public schools in Anambra State formed the sample for the study. Thirty (30) item structured questionnaires on a four-point rating scale developed by the researchers were used for data collection. A reliability coefficient of 0.88 was established using Cronbach Alpha techniques. After the administration of the instrument to the respondents, the data obtained were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research question and z-test to test the null hypothesis at the significance level of 0.05. The results obtained showed that male chemistry students are more aware of entrepreneurial development than their female counterparts. There is no significance difference between male and female chemistry students' level of awareness and on the challenges of entrepreneurial skill development. It was recommended that students should be encouraged to develop the ability to control one's own life, problem solving, creativity and interpersonal communication in chemistry. This should help the government and chemistry teachers to assist in ameliorating the predicaments in global educational system and help learners develop skills for self employment.

Keyword: Education, Chemistry, students, entrepreneurial skills, development, global, conflicts resolution, awareness.

Introduction

The globally emerging goals in the context of social and economic reforms have led to redefining of the nation's priorities in order to enhance productivity. Therefore, a nation with plans or aspirations for economic development and technological advancement cannot afford to neglect the development of human as a resource for productivity (Eniayeju, 2010). Buttressing the above assertion, Nnoli (2016) contributed that education; in its widest sense is any systematic influencing of people's knowledge, skill and attitudes. Such education not only serves obvious utilitarian purposes, but it most imperatively, cultivates and strengthens the will and the capacity of all people to accept worldwide responsibilities

and to escape self-destruction.

Education is an essential tool for human development and eradication of poverty. It is the key to success, that key that breaks the yoke of ignorance and superstition. Fundamentally, the objective of education should be to enable people initiate, understand and even anticipate changes in their environment and adjust accordingly. This is why Osisioma (2011) pointed that, in this competitive global economy, no nation can survive without developing the skills of its workforce. She maintained that, Nigeria is challenged to re-position itself in this new wave of globalization by re-evaluating its education policy to include a well-structured science and technology education that emphasizes knowledge creation and transfer,

critical thinking, problem solving, creativity and innovation.

Okeke (2010) is of the view that the final step in capacity building is the ability of a nation, a state or people to engage creatively in science education through entrepreneurial development, scientific research, development of new technologies and their applications to economics, social and human needs. Every nation of the world is endowed with one natural resources or the other, like mineral, water and human resources. The contribution of these to the national growth and development depends on the training received by human resources to put the other resources into effective use.

Chemistry is one of the most important branches of science which enables learners to understand what happens around them. It helps then to solve simple problems they encounter daily. Hence Udogu, (2009) stated that the most interesting aspect of chemistry is that it applies to our daily lives. According to Nnoli (2011), chemistry is a discipline which high standard of conduct must be amplified by teachers and researches in ways that students cannot fail to observe and adopt. She went further to note that the complexity of the task is such that one can no longer easily acquire the necessary skills without some formal instructions which plays a critical role on what students learnt in the chemistry classrooms.

Chemistry has helped so many people in the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills for self employment, especially this time we have scarcity of jobs due to socio- economic problems. The skills acquired in chemistry do not require any finding from abroad as their capital requirements are often moderate. Such skills are important because, in keeping with the principle of comparative advantage, they make use of available natural/human resources for maximum output and for sustainable development (Newbury, 2001). In chemistry there are many entrepreneurial skills for creativity and capacity building which will help to minimize the abstract nature of chemistry and ameliorate the global

problems of unemployment in our country, example, Production of wine from ethanol (Absolute alcohol), Air-refreshner, Disinfectant, Soaps, Detergents, Polish, Creams and so on.

Azuka (2003) defined entrepreneurs as innovators who use scientific, technological and business processes to change the status quo or the existing products and services to set up new products and services. Entrepreneurial skills are in-built capabilities or tools that enable an entrepreneur to carry out an entrepreneurial task. It is acquired by a person with high need for achievement. An entrepreneur possesses the following attributes: self-discipline, self-nurturing; highly energetic tolerant of uncertainty, innovativeness, action-oriented and ability to improvise. He is visionary, purposeful, energetic and a risk taker.

Conflict resolution is used interchangeably with dispute resolution where arbitration and litigation processes are critically involved; but in education it can be thought to encompass the use of nonviolent resistance measures by conflicted parties in an attempt to promote effective educational system. It is also defined as an explicit instruction of skills and strategies for having a peaceful, productive interactions with others (Melamed & Reiman, 2017). He maintained that conflict arises when one or more participants view the current system or relationship as not working. At least one party is so dissatisfied with the status quo, that he or she is willing to speak- up in hopes of improving the situation. Awareness, according to Nnoli (2016) is the state or level of consciousness where sense data can be confirmed by an observer. She maintained that it is a gradual passed from sleep to full awareness. It is also a state or quality of being aware of something. The awareness of one type of idea naturally fosters an awareness of another idea.

Problem Statement

There are conflicts in educational system because many graduates are unemployed. They do not possess appropriate skills needed

by the employees. Furthermore, most of these graduate are not aware of entrepreneurial skills that will enable them establish and manage a small business enterprise so as to become self-employed and self-reliant on graduation. There is need to resolve these conflicts by making science education in Nigeria more functional and meaningful to both youths and society at large. One of the best ways to achieve this is to make students be aware of entrepreneurial skills in chemistry education, to suggest possible way to inculcate these skills in them and finally identify likely challenges to this task. Therefore, this work sought to ascertain the following: The;

1. Chemistry students' awareness of development of entrepreneurial skills.
2. Possible challenges to the development of entrepreneurial skills among chemistry students.
3. Strategies for achieving the inculcation of entrepreneurial skills among chemistry students.
4. Gender difference in chemistry students' awareness of development of entrepreneurial skills.
5. Difference in the possible challenges to the development of entrepreneurial skills among male and females chemistry students.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of chemistry students' awareness of entrepreneurial skills development?
2. What are the possible challenges to the development of entrepreneurial skills among chemistry students?
3. What are the strategies for achieving the inculcation of entrepreneurial skills among chemistry students?
4. What is the gender difference in chemistry students' awareness of development of entrepreneurial skills?
5. What is the gender difference in the possible challenges to the development of entrepreneurial skills among male and female chemistry students?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Male and female chemistry students do not differ in their mean rating scores on their awareness of entrepreneurial skill development in chemistry.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female students on the possible challenges to the development of entrepreneurial skills among chemistry students.

Methods

A descriptive survey design was used for the study. The study was carried out in secondary schools in six education zones in Anambra State. The sample consists of 300 chemistry students drawn from 45 out of 258 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The population comprised of all chemistry education students (numbering 1,826 students) in 258 public secondary schools Anambra State. From each of the six education zones in Anambra State, 8 public secondary schools were drawn by simple random sampling with replacement, except in Otuocha zone from which 5 public secondary schools were selected because Otuocha zone has fewest secondary schools.

This instrument for data collection was 30 items in structured questionnaire on a four-point scale of strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed developed by the researcher. The questionnaire has two sections: Section A sought information on the bio-data of the respondents. Section B sought information on the awareness, challenges and a way out for the development of entrepreneurial skills among chemistry students. The instrument was validated by two chemistry educators and two experts in measurement and evaluation from University of Nigeria Nsukka. The comments and suggestions of the experts were incorporated in building up the final draft of the instrument. The research question was answered using mean and standard deviation. A mean of 2.50 and above indicated that the respondents agreed with items on the questionnaire while a mean below 2.50

indicated that the respondents disagreed with the items.

Table 1: Mean Rating Scores and Standard Deviation of Chemistry Students' Awareness of Entrepreneurial Skill Development

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Use materials to make chemistry concept more concrete and real.	2.87	0.82	Agreed
2	Linking chemistry concept teaching to the productions of many industrial items.	3.10	0.91	Agreed
3	Integrating theory with practical during teaching	2.90	0.85	Agreed
4	Move to industrial attachment to learn skills involved in the production of some chemicals.	3.29	0.83	Agreed
5	Carryout home projects requiring skills	2.96	0.93	Agreed
6	Students learn skills from resource persons outside school setting.	3.47	1.21	Agreed
7	Students always practicalize their chemistry lessons using the few available materials.	3.47	1.21	Agreed
8	Involving students in the preparation of materials for practical lessons.	3.56	1.54	Agreed
9	Carryout project works that can enable me acquire relevant skills.	3.56	1.54	Agreed
10	Read pamphlets that carry information on the skills and methods of production of consumer goods or production e.g. dettol, soap etc.	2.98	0.94	Agreed
	Average mean	3.22	1.08	Agreed

Table 1 shows that chemistry students are aware of entrepreneurial skill development.

Table 2: Mean Rating Scores and Standard Deviation of Students' Perception on the Challenges of Developing Entrepreneurial skills Among Chemistry Students.

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Most students lack the knowledge of skill acquisition for entrepreneurial development.	3.30	0.80	Agreed
2	Poor pay package of our parents	3.20	1.20	Agreed
3	Insufficient time for teachers to engage us in the use of these materials.	2.83	0.71	Agreed
4	Excess teaching load does not permit the inculcation of the skills.	2.92	0.82	Agreed

5	Lack of interest on the part of school head discourages teachers to develop entrepreneurial skills in students.	2.80	0.81	Agreed
6	Inadequate number of chemistry teachers who are prepared to use materials in the development of entrepreneurial skills in students.	3.50	0.50	Agreed
7	Cost effective nature on the assembling of those materials.	3.30	0.90	Agreed
8	Lack of social amenities necessary for the effective utilization of those materials during teaching.	2.52	0.90	Agreed
9	Lack of interest on the part of students on the consumption of principles and skills involved in these materials.	2.80	0.81	Agreed
10	Non-inclusion of the entrepreneurial education in secondary school curriculum.	3.40	0.90	Agreed
	Average mean	3.06	0.85	

The data reported on Table 2 shows that all the 10 items were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This shows that respondents agreed with the items in the questionnaire as the challenges for development of entrepreneurial skills among chemistry students.

Table 3: Mean Rating Scores and Standard Deviation of students' Perception on Strategies for achieving the Developing Entrepreneurship Education Among Chemistry Students.

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Ensuring that students are aware of entrepreneurial development.	3.42	0.62	Agreed
2	Government should include entrepreneurial education in secondary school curriculum.	3.06	0.91	Agreed
3	Enough time for teachers to engage us in the use of these materials.	3.00	0.87	Agreed
4	Teaching load should permit the inculcation of the skills.	2.95	1.04	Agreed
5	School heads should encourage teachers to develop entrepreneurial skills in students.	3.92	0.85	Agreed
6	Chemistry teachers should be encouraged to use materials to teach students for the development of entrepreneurial skills.	2.76	0.78	Agreed
7	Government should make finances available for the purchase and assembly of those materials.	3.30	0.82	Agreed
8	Accessibility of some of the important materials during s teaching.	2.82	0.81	Agreed

9	Social amenities necessary for the effective utilization of those materials during teaching should be made available.	2.58	0.58	Agreed
10	Development of interest on the part of students on the consumption of principles and skills involved in these materials.	2.63	1.01	Agreed
	Average mean	3.04	0.83	

The data reported on Table 3 shows that all the 10 items were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This shows that respondents agreed with the items in the questionnaire as the strategies for inculcating of entrepreneurial skills among chemistry students.

Table 4: Mean Response on the Awareness of Entrepreneurial Skill Development Among Male and Female Chemistry Students.

Group	N	X	SD
Male Students	165	1.91	0.58
Female students	135	1.30	0.48

Table 4 reveals that male students had a mean of 1.91 and a standard deviation of 0.58 while female students had a mean of 1.30 and a standard deviation of 0.48. This shows that male chemistry students are more aware of entrepreneurial skills development than female students.

Table 5: Mean Response on the Challenges for Development of Entrepreneurial Skill Among Male and Female Chemistry Students.

Group	N	X	SD
Male Students	165	1.90	0.50
Female students	135	1.14	0.33

Table 5 reveals that male students had a mean of 1.90 and a standard deviation of 0.50 while female students had a mean of 1.14 and a standard deviation of 0.33. This shows that male chemistry students have more challenges for the development of entrepreneurial skill than female students.

Table 6: Z-test of the mean ratings of male and female students on the awareness of entrepreneurial skill development among male and female chemistry students.

(P < 0.05)

Group	N	X	Sd	df	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Male Students	165	1.91	0.58	298	0.47	1.96	Accepted
Female Students	135	1.30	0.48				

Table 6 shows that the z-cal is 0.47. This value is less than the z-crit value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance (d/f = 298). This led the researchers to accept the null hypothesis that stated that male and female chemistry students do not differ in their perception on the awareness of

entrepreneurial skill development.

Table 7: Z-test of the mean ratings of male and female students on the challenges for development of entrepreneurial skill among chemistry students.

(P<0.05)							
Group	N	X	Sd	df	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Male Students	165	1.90	0.50	298	0.47	1.96	Accepted
Female Students	135	1.14	0.33				

Table 7 shows that the z-cal is 0.47. This value is less than the z-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance (d/f= 299). This led the researcher to accept the null hypotheses that stated that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female students on the challenges for development of entrepreneurial skill among chemistry students.

Discussion

The findings of this study showed that the chemistry students used in this study agreed that they are aware of entrepreneurial development but they do not have appropriate knowledge and skills for the development of entrepreneurship education. The chemistry students also agreed that they need time to up-date and develop their entrepreneurial knowledge and skills before they can impart same to other students through science teacher education. The findings also showed that the male chemistry students are more aware of entrepreneurial development and have more challenges than the female counterparts. There is no significance different between male and female chemistry students on their level of awareness and their challenges for entrepreneurial skill development. From the above findings there is clear evidence that chemistry education in Nigeria is not functional yet and this tallied with the observation made by Nnoli (2016) who maintained that Nigerian education is purely academic education. This is because teachers do not possess the prerequisite skills to teach chemistry effectively. The findings of this study also identified the challenges for the

development of entrepreneurial skills in secondary school students, through chemistry education to include the following: exclusion of entrepreneurship education from the secondary school curriculum, inadequate number of chemistry teachers who are prepared to use materials in the development of entrepreneurial skills, cost effective nature on the assembling of materials, lack of interest on the part of students, head teachers' discouragement and laboratory for the effective utilization of materials during teaching.

The importance of integration of entrepreneurial skill's into chemistry teaching instruction does not only end with helping the students to become self-reliant, but contribute toward building a sustainable national development. The chemistry teachers should therefore, be encouraged to integrate and help to develop more entrepreneurial skills into science teaching instruction for varieties of opportunities in the labour.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Curriculum planners should redesigned science teacher education programme to

include entrepreneurial skill acquisition which seems lacking in the present teacher education programme.

2. Curriculum planners should also reform curriculum to be competency based, interactive and problem-solving based teaching and learning which will provide students with necessary skills for future employment and self-reliance.
3. Teacher should enlighten students on the cost of materials for productions in order to make students realize the economic application of science to real life.
4. Students should be encouraged in the utilization of accumulated natural resources in the country in their productions for entrepreneurial skill development.
5. Professional development of the science teachers should be encouraged in order to keep the teachers abreast of the current issues in education and help them refine their professional practice with a focus on skills development.

Conclusion

Developing entrepreneurship skills in chemistry students are important, hence, the chemistry teacher should be adequately prepared to impart these skills to their students. Thus the inclusion of entrepreneurship education in various teacher education programmes is imperative because it will help to resolve global conflict in education. Acquiring these skills may also be of benefit to those who may not be able to make it to tertiary institutions. It may even serve as a means of making extra income for those who are already employed. This will guarantee youths future and create peaceful and prosperous society. Government on his

part should equip the secondary schools properly by providing facilities like science laboratories.

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